

Insect resistance

Rice resistance to thrips

R. Velusamy and S. Chelliah,
Agricultural Entomology Department,
Tamil Nadu Agricultural University,
Coimbatore 641003, India

The rice thrip *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall) sometimes reaches populations of economic significance in India. Thrips infest nursery seedlings and the early transplanted crop; they cause leaves to roll, then turn yellow. The plants wilt in severe cases.

From July to September 1979, thrips incidence was heavy in field nursery seedlings at Coimbatore. Based on the range of symptoms, a visual resistance rating scale was developed:

Damage	Rating scale	Grade
Rolling of terminal 1/3 area of 1st leaf only	1	Highly resistant
Rolling of terminal 1/3 to 1/2 area of 1st and 2d leaves	3	Resistant
Rolling of terminal 1/2 area of 1st, 2d, and 3d leaves; yellowing of leaf tips	5	Moderately resistant
Rolling of entire length of all leaves with pronounced yellowing	7	Susceptible
Complete plant wilting followed by severe yellowing and scorching	9	Highly susceptible

Using the rating scale, 25-day-old seedlings of 66 rice cultivars were screened in the field nursery.

Identified as highly resistant were Balamawee, Suduru Samba, Sinna Sivappu, Thirrisa, H105, and Perunel. The resistance of the first three varieties

to certain brown planthopper biotypes is of practical significance. Nine other varieties that were rated as resistant, and should be useful in resistance breeding programs, were ASD7, B2360-11-3-2-3, Babawee, CO29, IET4786, IR4432-52-6-4, Nira, PTB19, and Sudu Hondarwala. ■

Field reaction of rice cultivars to hispa and leaf folder

G. S. Dhaliwal, Punjab Agricultural University, Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala 144601, Punjab, India

A collection of 334 cultivars was assessed in the field in 1978 kharif for varietal differences in tolerance for rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* and rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. Fifty-day-old seedlings of the cultivars were transplanted in two lines, each 2.55-m long, at a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. The hispa and leaf folder-damaged leaves on 10 hills of each variety were counted at 40 and 75 days after transplanting, respectively.

None of the tested varieties was completely free from insect attack. For rice hispa, the lowest infestation (5 damaged leaves/10 hills) was on IET4109. Cultivars that had comparatively less damage (fewer than 10 damaged leaves/10 hills) were PR299 A, PR385, PR506, PR515, PR285, PR409, PR520, PR440, IET3578, IET5329, and IET6251. The most severely infested

cultivars (more than 80 damaged leaves/10 hills) included PR274, PR437, and CRM5713-13. CRM5713-13 had the highest damage, 93 leaves/10 hills.

For the rice leaf folder, IET625 1 was the least damaged (16 leaves/10 hills).

The most severely infested cultivars were PR299A, PR515, PR437, PR476, 1870, 1991, CRM5710-8, and CRM5761-1. CRM5761-1 had the highest damage, 96 leaves/10 hills. ■

Deep water

Thailand releases two new deepwater rice varieties

C. Prechachat, C. Setabutara, K. Kupkanchanakul, S. Amonsilpa, N. Supapoj, T. Kupkanchanakul, C. Boonwite, W. Sirikant, A. Wiengweera, N. Kongseree, and A. Sariaabutr. Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives, Bangkok, Thailand

Thai government officials formally approved the release of RD17 and RD19, new semidwarf rice varieties that are tolerant of water depths up to 1 meter, in December 1979. RD17 was previously known by its experimental line number

BKN6986-66-2 and RD19, as BKN6986-147-2. Both varieties were selected from the cross IR262/Pin Gaew 56, made in 1969 at the Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, with the objective of transferring deepwater tolerance and elongation ability from the Thai floating variety Pin Gaew 56 into progeny of the IR262 plant type. IR262 is a photoperiod insensitive semidwarf line obtained 13 years ago from IRR1.

Early generations were tested for deepwater tolerance at Klong Luang and Huntra Rice Experiment Stations and then selected for uniformity and yield at various rice stations and in farmers' fields in the Central Plain, where flooding

occurs annually. Yields of the better lines, including RD17 and RD19, averaged 3 to 4 t/ha; Pin Gaew 56 generally yielded 1 to 2 t/ha less. The yields varied depending on maximum water depth and amount of fertilizer applied. RD17 often averaged 4 t/ha when water depths did not exceed 1 m. Neither variety is recommended for areas where water depths are expected to exceed 1 m.

Both RD17 and RD19 are intended for the monsoon season because they mature too late for the dry-season crop. Also water depth is usually not a problem in the dry season and the present improved varieties such as RD7 perform satisfactorily there.

RD17 is insensitive to photoperiod, has a stiff straw, matures in about

140 days, can elongate its stem at 5 cm/day, and has withstood submergence for 7 days without serious injury. Its drought tolerance at early growth stages is an additional advantage. When grown in 80 cm of water RD17 has an average height of 160 cm (range, 150–170 cm). It is moderately resistant to bacterial blight but susceptible to the brown planthopper, stem borer, and gall midge. RD17 has brown rice kernels more than 7 mm long, with relatively low chalkiness and high amylose content. Its cooking and milling characteristics, however, are acceptable.

We believe that RD17 will become popular in occasionally flooded areas where farmers grow ordinary improved varieties. RD17's elongation ability would be flood insurance in such

high-risk areas. Furthermore, its photoperiod insensitivity will permit many farmers in flood-prone areas to harvest a crop in about 140 days. RD19 is sensitive to photoperiod, and has slightly higher grain chalkiness and better drought tolerance in the vegetative stage than RD17. RD19 usually ripens around mid-December, if planted in July or August. RD19 has acceptable milling and cooking qualities. Its greatest potential is anticipated in areas where farmers now plant only tall, traditional, photoperiod-sensitive types because monsoon floods might destroy ordinary improved varieties. Furthermore, because of its better plant type, RD19 is expected to be more fertilizer responsive than traditional varieties. ■

Structural analysis of the nematode population and the source of ufra

P. G. Cox, L. Rahman, and M. A. Hannan, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI)-Overseas Development Agency (ODA) Deepwater Rice Pest Management Project, BRRI, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

Ufra caused by the rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev is a serious disease of deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. Cox and Rahman (IRRN 4:3 [June 1979], 10–11) have suggested how structural analysis of the nematode population (i.e. determination of the relative frequency with which different population sizes occur in individual tillers) might be used to identify the source of inoculum according to the presence of a distinct mode at high populations. The presence early in the season of heavily infested tillers might be evidence of primary infestation from diseased residues in the field at sowing, well before flooding.

At BRRI two blocks of deepwater rice (variety Gorcha) were broadcast on 10 April 1979 in a deepwater tank especially constructed for ufra research. At the time of broadcast the larger block (8 × 8 m) was inoculated with 100 infested panicles retained from the previous season; the smaller block

Structure of the ufra nematode population with and without basal inoculation. BRRI, 1979.

(8 × 4 m) was not inoculated. The tank was flooded from early June onward. Active *D. angustus* were collected from a farmer's field and dispersed in the tank on 16 June to simulate secondary infestation by water-borne inoculum. The structure of the nematode populations in the two blocks was analyzed at the end of August through the procedure described by Cox and Rahman.

The two population structures differed greatly (see figure). The plot with basal inoculation had a much greater percentage of infested tillers and average number of nematodes per tiller. The population structure in the inoculated plot also had a distinct right-hand mode representing about 2.5% of all tillers (av no. of nematodes/infested tiller in the RH mode, 5500; s.d, 3700). This mode did not occur in the